

PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF FORMING POSITIVE ATTITUDES TOWARD FAMILY VALUES IN FEMALE UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the psychological and practical foundations for forming positive attitudes toward family values among female university students. The study, through experimental analysis, revealed the positive impact of socio-psychological training sessions on the development of key components such as responsibility, cohesion, and stability. Based on statistical data, it was confirmed that the training programs contributed to the development of participants' emotional intelligence, as well as interpersonal and intrapersonal skills. Post-training results were measured using the "Assessment of Positive Attitudes Toward Family Values in Female Students" questionnaire and E.D. Lyusin's "Emotional Intelligence" diagnostic method, followed by psychometric analysis.

The findings demonstrated a strong relationship between the formation of positive attitudes and psychological readiness for family life. The study concludes that socio-psychological training promotes more conscious, responsible, and stable attitudes toward family values among female students.

Introduction. In today's conditions of globalization and accelerated information flow, the formation of strong family values in the minds of young people, especially female students, is emerging as one of the important socio-psychological tasks. The sustainable development of society, the strengthening of its spiritual and moral foundations directly depend on the health of the family, the culture of relationships in it, intergenerational cohesion and the inheritance of values. It is precisely young students, as individuals who will actively participate in family relations in the future, play an important role in family management and child upbringing, who today need to form a positive attitude towards family values and stable psychological preparation. Such an approach serves as one of the main factors in building a socio-economic, spiritual and culturally developed society. This scientific article analyzes psychological trainings, exercises aimed at increasing the level of emotional intelligence in the formation of positive attitudes towards family values in female students, and their effectiveness. Through training programs, the development of such basic

psychological components as responsibility, solidarity and stability is monitored, and the results obtained are scientifically substantiated on the basis of psychometric indicators. The relevance of the article is determined by the need to develop psychological approaches that ensure the thorough preparation of female students for family life, especially against the backdrop of current social changes. The use of socio-psychological training sessions aimed at forming positive attitudes towards family values in female students, as well as individual and group work (interviews, meetings, psychotraining and other activities) with female students and their parents, tutors, was reflected in the subsequent results.

The comparative state of the indicators of the formation of positive attitudes towards family values in female students after the training program was analyzed. A comparative analysis was carried out on the basis of psychometric requirements for the average quantitative indicators of the indicators before and after the application of the psychotraining program.

Psychotraining aimed at ensuring the formation of positive attitudes towards family values in female students was organized for all female students involved in our research. The results after the psychotraining program showed that the components representing positive attitudes towards family values in female students were developed.

Now let's move on to the analysis of the empirical results obtained directly after the training program implemented among female students.

After our training programs that developed the questionnaire "Determining the level of formation of positive attitudes towards family values in female students", significant differences were noted in all factors in our experimental group. In particular, significant changes were observed in the factors "responsibility" ($t = -2.4$; $p < 0.05$), "cohesion" ($t = -2.5$; $p < 0.05$) and "stability" ($t = -2.9$; $p < 0.05$). These results confirm the effective impact of the training program, indicating that female students have increased their sense of responsibility in family relationships, maintaining team spirit, and striving to ensure stability. Female students who participated in the training learned to take their family responsibilities more seriously and understood the importance of family unity and collective decision-making.

They also successfully mastered the strategies necessary to achieve stability in family life. These changes have created a positive dynamic in their attitudes towards family values, indicating that female students are more prepared for family life and have strengthened their positions. The theoretical knowledge and practical exercises provided during the training program have led to a deeper understanding of their family responsibilities and relationships. Female students have begun to feel more deeply the importance of being responsible in family relationships, ensuring family unity, and maintaining a stable family.

These changes also reflect the impact of family values on personal development, that is, they indicate that the girls' personalities and responsibilities in social relationships have been strengthened. In addition, as a result of the positive impact of correctional programs, positive attitudes towards family values, aimed at strengthening responsibility, solidarity and stability, have been effectively developed in female students. This helps them find their place in family life as successful and responsible individuals and further strengthen the family environment.

Table 1

Comparative analysis of the results obtained through the questionnaire “Determining the level of formation of positive attitudes towards family values among female students” (n=328)

№	Components	Groups	Pre-workout	Post-raining	Differentiation	
			M	M	t	p
1.	Responsibility	Experimental group (n=128)	4,1	6,9	-2,4	0,05
		Control group (n=200)	4,4	5,1	-1,8	0,18
2.	Social Responsibility	Experimental group (n=128)	5,3	7,4	-2,5	0,05
		Control group (n=200)	5,6	6,2	-1,4	0,14
3.	Sustainability	Experimental group (n=128)	5,1	7,2	-2,9	0,05
		Control group (n=200)	5,5	6,0	-1,1	0,12

The essence of these general changes is that the trainings have formed a more positive and conscious approach to family values in female students. The theoretical knowledge and practical exercises provided during the training programs have led to a deeper understanding of their family responsibilities and relationships. Female students have begun to feel more deeply the importance of being responsible in family relationships, ensuring family unity, and maintaining family stability. At the same time, the results obtained demonstrate the effectiveness achieved through the trainings in the formation of relationships based on mutual trust and respect. Female students have sought to participate more actively in maintaining stability and community in their families, and to solve family problems together. These changes also reflect the impact of family values on personal development, that is, the girls' personalities and responsibilities in social relationships have been strengthened.

In particular, as a result of the positive impact of developmental training programs, positive attitudes towards family values, aimed at strengthening responsibility, solidarity and stability, were effectively formed in female students. This helps them find their place in family life as successful and responsible individuals and further strengthen the family environment. These results mean that the trainings expanded the female students' understanding of family values and helped them to understand more deeply that the family is an important social

institution. The female students deeply felt that family responsibility is not only an obligation, but also plays an important role in ensuring family peace and stability. Through the practical skills acquired during the trainings, they learned to solve family problems more effectively and work collaboratively with other family members. The results also had a positive impact on the development of the female students' social skills. For example, in the process of making family decisions, female students learned to express their opinions clearly and confidently, which served to maintain family unity and increase mutual respect between family members. In turn, the desire for stability further strengthened the desire of girls to create a solid foundation in their future family life. The results of the training also show that significant changes have occurred in the attitude of female students towards family values, and these changes are of great socio-psychological importance. During the training, the girls better understood how family values affect individual development and took steps towards becoming socially mature individuals. Thus, changes in all factors created the basis for a deeper understanding of the female students' approaches to family life and the formation of more responsible, united and stable individuals.

Table 2

Comparative analysis of the level of emotional intelligence development of female students (based on E.D. Lyusin's "Emotional Intelligence" questionnaire).

№	Name of factors	Before the experiment				Post-experiment				Statistical difference	
		M11	S11	M21	S21	M12	S12	M22	S22	t	p
1	Interpersonal emotional intelligence	19,24	1,42	21,48	2,03	25,56	1,03	24,28	1,12	2,1	0,05
2	Intrinsic emotional intelligence	14,36	1,04	15,21	1,63	20,19	0,68	19,43	0,89	1,9	0,01
3	Understanding emotions	14,11	2,28	14,03	1,95	18,14	1,76	18,02	1,14	2,3	0,05
4	Managing emotions	10,12	1,32	12,01	1,76	14,47	1,29	15,01	1,29	2,1	0,05
5	Understanding the emotions of others	5,62	1,13	5,17	2,07	11,73	0,91	11,41	1,08	2,5	0,05
6	Managing the emotions of others	24,52	1,46	24,31	1,78	36,16	0,86	35,68	1,01	1,4	0,01
7	Understanding one's own emotions	30,28	2,04	32,87	2,31	42,14	1,43	41,97	2,07	1,8	0,05
8	Managing one's own emotions	31,29	1,33	32,34	1,18	45,03	1,14	46,15	1,38	2,1	0,05
9	Controlling one's own emotions from external influences	32,13	1,11	32,39	1,92	46,54	1,05	43,52	1,76	1,3	0,01

Note: M1- engaged girls (n=148); M2- unengaged girls (n=180).

The comparative analysis of the results of our study on the emotional intelligence factors of female students based on the questionnaire "Emotional Intelligence" by E.D. Lucin

showed that due to the effective impact of the applied developmental programs, an increase was observed in both groups of participants. As can be seen from the comparative table above, all factor indicators in both sexes differentiated significantly in the control experiment compared to the experimental experiment.

The increase in the interpersonal emotional intelligence factor by 6.32 points in engaged girls and by 2.80 points in unengaged girls is significant, as it further expands their ability to understand the emotions of others, especially family members ($M_{12}=25.56$; $M_{22}=24.28$). In addition, the improvement of the interpersonal relationship system helps them to adapt to family life more easily through communication and listening to others. Based on our observations, since it has been shown that misunderstandings in family relationships, verbal conflicts, mutual disrespect, and lack of distance in communication are the main reasons for the separation of families, we believe that the development of interpersonal emotional intelligence at the required level is important for female students to easily adapt to family life and prevent various conflict situations and fulfill their social roles without shortcomings ($t=2.1$).

A significant increase was also observed in the internal emotional intelligence factor, with an increase of 4.10 points in engaged girls and 3.90 points in unengaged girls, which serves to demonstrate the ability of girls to understand and manage their emotions ($M_{12}=20.19$; $M_{22}=19.43$). The ability of brides to consciously and correctly understand and manage their emotions in any difficult situations contributes to the well-being of the family. The fact that the overall indicators of the participants on this factor showed a high average value can be assessed as the effect of both the applied program and the education and upbringing carried out by the employees of the higher education system ($t=1.9$).

The increase in the factor of understanding emotions (3.03 points in engaged girls, 3.99 points in unengaged girls, $M_{12}=18.43$; $M_{22}=17.12$) leads to the fact that female students, especially engaged girls, demonstrate the ability to understand their own and others' (family members') emotions. In particular, the ability to adequately assess one's own emotions contributes to self-satisfaction, the formation of an active positive attitude towards family and personal life, and the deeper one understands family values and acts on them, the more accurately one feels the demands placed on daughters-in-law by family members, which leads to a faster finding of one's place in the family and gaining respect ($t=2.3$).

Indeed, scientific research and data from real-life situations have proven that girls often have a relatively low ability to control their emotions, which leads to various negative consequences. In relationships with family members and others, they are very likely to experience negative experiences (affect, frustration, stress, anxiety, nervousness, etc.). The fact that they do not fall into such negative situations depends on the development of their ability to control their emotions. The increase in the factor of emotion management (an increase of 3.35 points in engaged girls and 3.00 points in unengaged girls, $M_{12}=14.47$; $M_{22}=15.01$) is explained by the development of their ability to manage their own and others' emotions and is significant in that it serves to eliminate negative situations such as the above. It should be noted that among the participants there are also girls who achieved high results on this factor ($t=2.1$). The increase in the factor of understanding the emotions of others (an increase of 6.09 points in engaged girls and 6.24 points in unengaged girls, $M_{12}=11.73$;

M22=11.41) is due to the ability of female students to perceive external manifestations of their emotions (facial expressions, gestures, vocal sounds) and to intuitively understand a person's emotional state; It indicates a relatively increased sensitivity to the internal states of those around them, which helps them to adapt more easily to family life. In particular, we believe that the ability to easily understand the emotions of the future spouse and his family members is a positive quality that ensures satisfaction with their family and life ($t=2.5$).

A high level of increase in the factor of managing the emotions of others (an increase of 11.64 points in engaged girls and 11.37 points in unengaged girls, $M_{12}=36.16$; $M_{22}=35.68$) is associated with the ability to arouse other positive emotions in them,

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